

Existence of Health Risk Behaviors (HRB) and associated factors among university student in Kathmandu District, 2024 AD

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Background: Drinking alcohol, smoking, and abusing drugs, eating too much salt, fat, and sugar, leading a sedentary lifestyle, consuming tainted or adulterated food, accidents, acting violently, and having unprotected sex are all health risks that university students around the world are extremely concerned about. Long-term effects on students' health and wellness could result from these behaviors. Health risk behaviors must be understood and addressed for health promotion initiatives to be successful.

Methodology: The prevalence of health risk behaviors and associated determinants was investigated using descriptive cross-sectional research with university students in the Kathmandu area. A semi-structured questionnaire that was created by the students themselves was used to collect data from 500 pupils. In SPSS version 16, descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyze the data.

Result: 250 (50%) of the 500 responders were from the health stream, 320 (64%) were female, 180 (36%) were male, and 250 (50%) were from the non-health stream. Of the 500 respondents, 123 (24.6%) engaged in unacceptable health risk behaviors (i.e., 5–11 HRBs), whereas 377 (75.4%) engaged in acceptable health risk behaviors (i.e., 0–4 HRBs). The following factors were statistically substantially associated with the respondent's level of HRBs: religion ($p=0.003$), age category ($p=0.001$), education streams ($p=0.001$), father's education ($p=0.048$), and principal source of family income ($p=0.001$), in that order. According to the results, HRBs were common in the health stream.

Conclusion: The study came to the conclusion that university students were heavily engaged in health risk behaviors during their time there and that these behaviors were widely accepted. According to this, university students need to be given an intervention for health risk behaviors, and the curriculum should be updated to include more material on these topics.

INTRODUCTION

Health risk behaviors, such as consumption of alcohol, tobacco, and drug abuse, consumption of too salty, fatty, and sugary foods, habit of sedentary living, improper waste disposal practices, mode of air, water, and living space pollutions, consumption of unsafe foods (Contaminated and adulterated), accidents, practices of violence and Multiple sexual partner share significant concerns among university students worldwide. These behaviors can have long-term adverse effects on students' health and well-being. Understanding the prevalence and associated factors of health risk behaviors among university. To create successful health promotion treatments, it is essential to comprehend the frequency and contributing elements of health risk behaviors among college students (Purbanchal University, 2019).

The main causes of illness, death, and social issues among teenagers are health-risky behaviors like smoking cigarettes, carrying a weapon, and engaging in unprotected sexual activity. Thus, there exist multiple reasons for gathering information on these and other habits that pose a risk to one's health (National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, 2012).

Health risk behaviors are defined as acts that increase the risk of disease or injury, which can subsequently lead to social problems, disability, and/or death. The most common high-risk behaviors include violence, alcoholism, tobacco use disorder, risky sexual behaviors, and eating disorders (Tariq, 2023) .

These activities are considered health risk behaviors because they are among the main causes of morbidity disability social problems and death in people. Risky health behaviors are frequently formed in childhood and adolescence and persist into adulthood. A complex range of biological psychological and social developmental changes occur during the adolescent stage. Health-risky behaviors are also thought to be a major contributor to avoidable early mortality. The youth risk behavior surveillance systems measure the following six key health-risk behavior categories: actions that result in violence and unintentional harm Sexual practices that increase the risk of unintended pregnancy and sexually transmitted diseases like HIV Use of alcohol and other drugs Use of tobacco Poor eating patterns with a sedentary or fat way of living (Sanjaya Kumar Shah, 2021).

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive cross-sectional study design was used to find out the existence of health risk behaviors and associated factors among university student of Kathmandu District from 2024/04/14 to 2024/07/13. Kathmandu district was chosen conveniently. The self-administered questionnaire was used for data collection tools. Firstly, a formal written letter was taken from the Nepal Institute of Health Sciences (NIHS) and will be delivered to university affiliated college which was selected from a systematic sampling method for permission. Self-introduction and the purpose of the research were explained to the focal person, when permission was given then select the sample unit and distribution of a set of self-administered questionnaires was distributed and informed consent was taken, and then only data was collected.

Pretesting of the tool was done at 10% i.e. 50 sample from similar groups before final data collection and Cronbach's alpha was tested and result was 0.86 that is reliability test of tool to find Consistency and accuracy of the collected data was checked on the same day to avoid missing or incomplete information.

RESULTS

All the calculated data were analyzed through SPSS version 25 and interpreted on the basis of research objectives, and research hypothesis and presented in tables. The findings of the study are presented in the following tables:

Table 1 Sociodemographic information of respondents

Variables	Categorical variables	Frequency (n=500)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	180	36 %
	Female	320	64%
Age in years	15-19	174	34.8%
	20-24	224	44.8%
	25-29	82	16.4%
	30-34	16	3.2%
	35-39	2	0.4%
40-44		2	0.4%
Education Stream	Health	250	50%
	Non-Health	250	50%
Types of Family	Single	276	55.2%
	Joint	206	41.2%
	Extended	18	3.6%

Religion			
Religion	Hindu	355	71%
	Buddhist	90	18%
	Christian	39	7.8%
	Muslim	12	2.4%
	Others	4	0.8%
Ethnicity			
Ethnicity	Dalit	35	7%
	Janjati	177	35.4%
	Madheshi	27	5.4%
	Muslim	15	3%
	Bramin/Chetri	240	48%
	Others	6	1.2%
Fathers Education			
Fathers Education	Illiterate	46	9.2%
	Literate (Read and Write)	77	15.4%
	Primary (0-8) Level	119	23.8%
	Secondary (8-12) Level	182	36.4%
	Higher (12 and above) Level	76	15.2%
Mothers Education			
Mothers Education	Illiterate	103	20.6%
	Literate (Read and Write)	129	25.8%
	Primary (0-8) Level	146	29.4%
	Secondary (8-12) Level	82	16.4%
	Higher (12 and above) Level	40	8%
Source of Family Income			
Source of Family Income	Agriculture	179	35.8%
	Service	88	17.6%
	Business	103	20.6%
	Daily Wages	35	7%
	Foreign Employment	95	19%

Table 2 Status of Existence of Health Risk Behaviors

Major Category of HRBs	Name of HRBs	Frequency	Percentage
Substance-Related HRBs	Alcohol intake	126	25.2
	Tobacco product intake	69	13.8
	Substance abuse	17	3.4
Food-related HRBs	Salty food intake	161	32.2
	Oily food intake	195	39
	Sugary food intake	209	41.8
	Junk food intake	488	97.6
Action-related HRBs	Sedentary Living	198	39.6
	Accident while driving	166	33.2
	Experience with physical violence allegations	59	11.8
	Engage with multiple sexual partners	38	7.6

Table 2 illustrates that one-fourth (25.2%) of the respondents took alcohol whereas 13.8 % of the respondents took tobacco and 3.4% took substances similarly, 97.6% of the respondents had consumed junk food, 41.8% of the respondents had sugary food intake, 39% of the respondents the respondent had oily food intake whereas 32.2% of the respondents had extra salt in their food. In addition, 39.6% of the respondents are living sedentary lifestyles, 33.2% of the respondents suffer from accidents while driving, 11.8% of the respondents experience physical violence allegations where as 7.6% of the respondents are involved in multiple sexual partners.

Table 3 Status of existence of Substance-related Health risk behaviors among university students and their associated factors

Major Category of HRBs	Name of HRBs	Peer Influence	Academic Stress	Socio Environmental	Low Economic Status	Curiosity	Others
Substance-Related HRBs	Alcohol intake (N=126)	48 (38.1%)	13 (10.3%)	18 (14.3%)	7 (5.6%)	39 (31%)	1 (0.8%)
	Tobacco product	21 (30.4%)	13 (18.8%)	16 (23.2%)	5 (7.2%)	13 (18.8%)	1 (1.4%)

intake (N=69)						
Substance abuse (N=17)	2 (11.8%)	3 (17.6%)	2 (11.8%)	1 (5.9%)	8 (47.1%)	1 (5.9%)

Table 4 shows that 38.1% of the respondents had alcohol due to peer influence, 31% of the respondents had alcohol due to curiosity whereas, only 0.8% had alcohol due to others factors. Likewise, 30.4% of the respondents had tobacco product due to peer influence, 23.2% of the respondents had tobacco product due to social environmental factor but only 1.4% of the respondents had tobacco due to others factor. Similarly, 47.1% of the respondents had substance abuse due to curiosity, 11.8% of the respondent had substance abuse due to peer influence while 5.9% of the respondents had substance due to others factor.

Table 4 Status of existence of Food-related Health risk behaviors among university students and their associated factors

Major Category of HRBs	Name of HRBs	Family influence	Peer Influence	Curiosity	Better Taste	Others
Food-related HRBs	Salty food intake	25 (16.6%)	14 (9.3%)	14 (9.3%)	96 (63.6%)	2 (1.3%)
	Oily food intake	106 (21.2%)	72 (14.4%)	99 (19.8%)	220 (44%)	3 (0.6%)
	Sugary food intake	45 (20.5%)	20 (9.1%)	9 (4.1%)	22 (10%)	123 (24.6%)
	Junk food intake	9 (1.8%)	48 (9.8%)	138 (28.1%)	272 (55.4%)	24 (4.9%)
						(N=491)

Table 5 illustrates that 63.6% of the respondents had additional salt in food for better taste, 16.6% of the respondents had additional salt in food due to family influence while only 1.3% of the respondents had additional

salt in the food due to other factors. In addition, 44% of the respondents had oily food for better taste, 21.2% of the respondents had oily food due to family influence whereas only 0.6% of the respondents had oily food due to other factors. Similarly, 24.6% of the respondents had sugar food due to other factors, 20.5% of the respondents had sugar food due to family influence and 4.1% of the respondents had sugar food due to curiosity. Likewise, 55.4% of the respondents had junk food for better taste, 28.1% of the respondents had junk food due to curiosity whereas 1.8% of the respondents had junk food due to family influence.

Table 4 Status of existence of Action-related Health risk behaviors among university students and their associated factors

Major Category of HRBs	Name of HRBs	Alcohol Consumption	Substance Abuse	Time Limitation	Peer Influence	Curiosity	Others
Action-related HRBs	Sedentary Living	17 (8.6%)	6 (3%)	52 (26.3%)	75 (37.9%)	39 (19.7%)	9 (4.5%)
	Accident while driving	11 (6.6%)	5 (3.6%)	92 (55.4%)	24 (14.5%)	25 (15.1%)	8 (4.8%)
	Experience with physical violence allegations	10 (16.9%)	3 (5.1%)	25 (42.4%)	20 (33.9%)	1 (1.7%)	0
	Engage with multiple sexual partners	4 (10.8%)	1 (2.7%)	2 (5.4%)	16 (43.2%)	14 (37.8%)	0
							(N=37)

Table 6 illustrates that 37.9% of the respondents had a sedentary lifestyle due to peer influence whereas 26.3% of the respondents had sedentary living due to time limitation, and 3% of the respondents had sedentary living due to substance abuse. Similarly, 55.4% of the respondents were having accidents while driving due to time limitations, 15.1% were having accidents while driving due to curiosity whereas 3.6% of the respondents were having accidents while driving due to substance abuse. Likewise, 42.4% of the respondents experienced physical violence

allegations due to time limitations 33.9% had physical violence allegations due to peer influence where and 1.7% of the respondents had physical violence allegations due to curiosity. In addition, 43.2% engaged in multiple sexual partners due to peer pressure, 37.8% engaged in multiple sexual partners due to curiosity, and 2.7% engaged due to substance abuse.

Table 5 Level of Existence of Health Risk Behaviors

Existence of Health Risk Behaviors			
Existence of Health Behaviors	Risk	Frequency	Percent
Low Risk (Having 0-4 Health Risk Behaviors)		377	75.4
High Risk (Having 5-11 Health Risk Behaviors)		123	24.6
Total		500	100.0

Table 6 illustrate that 75.4% of the respondents had low risk HRBs whereas 24.6% of the respondents had high risk (Having 5-11 Health Risk Behaviors).

Table 7 Association between the existence of HRBs and sociodemographic information of respondents

Variables	Existence of HRBs		Chi-square (X ²)	p-value
	Low risk	High risk		
Age Groups				
<20 Years	198 (39.6%)	179 (35.8%)	11.454	0.001
>20 Years	43 (8.6%)	80 (16%)		
Sex				
Male	129 (25.8%)	51 (10.2%)	2.113	0.146
Female	248 (49.6%)	72 (14.4%)		
Education Stream				
Health	166 (33.2%)	84(16.8%)	21.835	0.001
Non-Health	211 (42.2%)	39 (7.8%)		
Family types				
Single	199 (39.8 %)	77 (15.4%)	3.614	0.057
Joint and extended	178 (35.6%)	46 (9.2%)		
Religion				

Hindu	282 (56.4%)	73 (14.6%)	10.754	0.001
Other than Hindu	95 (19%)	50 (10%)		

Ethnicity				
Brahmin/Chetri	182 (36.4%)	62 (12.4%)	0.023	0.879
Other caste	194 (38.8%)	62 (12.4%)		

Father's Education Status				
Up to basic level (0-8 class)	192 (38.4%)	50 (10%)	3.923	0.048
More than basic level (above 8 class)	185 ((37%)	73 (14.6%)		

Mother's Education Status				
Up to basic level (0-8 class)	285 (57%)	93 (18.6%)	0.001	0.989
More than basic level (above 8 class)	92 (18.4%)	30 (6%)		

Main Source of Family Income				
Agriculture, service, and business	296(59.2%)	74 (14.8%)	16.234	0.001
Daily wages, foreign employment, and others	81 (16.2%)	49 (9.8%)		

Table 7 illustrates that there is a significant association between age group, education stream, religion, father's education, source of family income.

DISCUSSION

The present study showed that 64% respondents were female and 36% of the respondents were male which is similar to the finding of a study conducted in Pokhara valley in which number of students were female (65.1%) while in students were male (34.9%) (Kamal Ranabhat, 2020).

The study showed that 75.4% of the respondents were age <20 years and 24.6% of the respondents were >20 years of age and the mean age was 21.56 years. Which is similar to findings of the study conducted in Kathmandu valley were majority of respondents were between aged 17-

20 years (76.8%) (Sanjaya Kumar Shah, 2021). The study showed that 25.2% of the respondents consumed alcohol, 13.8% of the respondents consumed tobacco products and only 3.4% of the respondents consume drugs which is similar to finding of the study conducted in Kathmandu Valley where 18.4% of the respondents drink alcohol, 6.4% of the respondents smoked cigarette and 6.8% of the respondents take drugs (Sanjaya Kumar Shah, 2021). The study shows that 71% of the respondents belong to Hindu religion and 29% of the respondents belong to other religion which is similar to the finding of a study conducted in Kathmandu Valley where 76.8% of the respondents belonged from Hindu religion (Sanjaya Kumar Shah, 2021).

The study finding revealed that 25.6% of the respondents drink alcohol and out of them 38.1% consumed due to peer influence, 31% consumed due to curiosity, 14.3% consumed due to socio-environmental factor, 10.3% due to academic stress and 6.6% consumed due to low economic status which is similar to the finding of a study conducted in Suryabinayak Municipality, Bhaktapur survey showed that female who drank in the past 12 months mostly drank 1-3 times a year (25.7%) and male who drank in the past 12 months mostly drank once a month (23.6%). Results showed that majority of the respondents (38.6%) were found to consume alcohol 1-3 times a year (P. Thapa, et al., 2016) and factors associated with peer pressure (70.58%) followed by their curiosity (29.42%) (Sanjaya Kumar Shah, 2021).

The study finding revealed that 13.8% of the respondents consume tobacco products and out of them 30.4% consumed due to peer influence, 18.8% consumed due to curiosity, 23.2% consumed due to socio-environmental factor, 18.8% due to academic stress and 7.2% consumed due to low economic status which is likely similar to the finding of a study conducted in 22.8% prevalence rate in consumption of tobacco among students and were found to be consuming tobacco due to the influence of friends (62.26%) and curiosity (37.74%), and that difference might be due to differ in methodology (Pragati Sharma, 2021). The study finding revealed that 3.4% of the respondents consume illegal drugs and which is similar to the finding of the study in which 8.8% of the respondents consume illegal drugs and difference might be due to depth of the study (Bimala Panthee, 2017).

The study findings revealed that 32.2% of respondents consumed salty food i.e. average 8.2 g/day and the major factor influencing salty food intake was better taste i.e. 63.6% and which is similar to the study in which 81.6% consumed 8g/day salty food (Kamal Ghimire, 2019). The study finding revealed that 39% respondents consumed oily food i.e. average 39.69 g/day and major factor influencing oily food intake was better taste i.e. 44% and which is similar to the study in Kerala India and in which 41.5% consume oily food 48.6 g/day (Gautam Parmar, 2024). The study finding revealed that 41.8% respondents consumed sugar i.e. average 61.8 g/day and major factor influencing sugar intake was better taste i.e. 56.16% and which is similar to the study in Free Sugar

Consumption and Obesity in European Adolescents in which 49.7% respondents consume sugar i.e. 87.5g/day (Sondos M. Flieh, 2020). The study finding revealed that 97.6% respondents consumed junk food and major factor influencing junk food intake was better taste i.e. 55.4% and which is similar to the study in majority (81%) of the students considered junk food consumption to be unhealthy (Sandip Pahari, 2020).

The study finding revealed that 39.6% of the respondents living sedentary lifestyle i.e. body movement less than 30 minutes per day and major factors influencing sedentary lifestyle was peer influence 37.9% which is similar to the study 45% adolescent didn't meet criteria of physical activities (Kiran Thapa, 2019). The study finding revealed that 33.2% of the respondents experienced accident while driving and major factors influencing experienced accident while driving was time limitation (Hatar) 37.9% which is not similar to the study 11% which might be due to different sample group (Meghnath Dhimal, 2019). The study finding revealed that 11.8% of the respondents experienced physical violence allegation and major factors influencing experienced physical violence allegations was time limitation (Hatar) 42.4% which is similar to the study 45% experienced physical violence (P. Thapa, 2016). The study findings revealed that 7.6% of the respondents were engaging with multiple sexual partners and the major factor influencing engaging with multiple sexual partners was peer influence 43.2% which is similar to the study 6.9% (Niranjan Shrestha, 2012).

LIMITATION

Only 11 health risk behaviors were selected for study out of 16 health risk behaviors found from the literature review due to study limitation and Only five health colleges and five non-health colleges (Total ten colleges) was selected for my study. The study was carried out in researcher's own financial effort. Data collection time was limited to two weeks only.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the existence of health-risk behaviors among university students was highly adopted. The result of the study showed that much more concerted efforts need to minimize respondent's status of health-risk behaviors.

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RECOMMENDATION

1. for local, provincial and federal government

The government can initiate comprehensive health education program to minimize the existence of health risk behaviors. Government can initiatives for the promotion of healthy behaviors. Government can initiate (law, regulation, act) policy enforcement for control of Health risk behaviors

2. for Universities and Colleges

Curriculum should be revised with the addition of content related to Health risk behaviors. There should be Encourage parental involvement in promoting healthy behaviors among students. There should be promotion of healthy behaviors in colleges and university settings. There should be research and continuous improvement in health risk behaviors related intervention's effectiveness

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